

Contribution of The Catholic Church to Financial Resources and Infrastructural Development of Secondary Schools in Kenya: A Case Study of Kisii Central Sub - County

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ABSTRACT: The Kenya's Basic Education Act 2013 empowers religious sponsors to participate in management of schools that they sponsor with regard to appointment of principals, provision of instructional, financial and infrastructural development of the schools. In Kisii Central Sub-County, the Catholic Church participates in management of 29(39.7%) secondary schools. However, queries were being raised on the current contribution of the church as it had come to the fore that most sponsored schools were experiencing crises that had tended to be linked to the church's participation in management. For instance, out of 29 principals in the sub-county, 18 (62.07%) new principals; 23 (79.31%) deputy principals and 5 (17.24%) BOM chair persons were rejected by the church from assuming their positions between 2010 - 2013 in the Sub-County which was higher compared to neighbouring Sub-Counties, that is, Marani 1(4.54%) and Kisii South 2 (7.41%) Principals; while Masaba 3 (12%) and Sameta 3 (13.04%) both involving Board of Management. The objectives of the study were to determine the contribution of the Catholic Church to financial resources and ascertain the contribution of the Catholic Church to infrastructural development to management of public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. The findings of this study were that the Catholic Church contribution to financial support for administrative staff, motivation and student bursaries was 27.7%; Infrastructural development in terms of provision for classrooms and land was 36.4%. this implies that the Catholic Church contribution to financial resources and infrastructural resources was critical and acknowledged by the School Boards of Management.

KEY WORDS: Contribution of The Catholic Church, Financial Resources, Infrastructural Development of Secondary Schools, Kenya: A Case Study of Kisii Central Sub - County

INTRODUCTION

During the eighteenth century, the clergy managed education in Kenya. They built new schools, financed them, recruited and trained teachers, oversaw the implementation of the curriculum, taught catechism and approved new teaching approaches (Republic of Kenya, 1994). On the other hand the state supported the churches by granting land and dispensing annual subsidies to support the Native missions. By 1920, the missionaries were increasingly committed to education not only to meet the demands of converts but also forestall any attempts by the government to monopolize education (Sheffield, 2009). Overtime, the government set up their own schools; to promote the colonial segregation policy for the Europeans, Asians and Africans as per the Fraser Commission, 1909. The Churches used Corresponding schools they had set up as an evangelizing medium, while the government initiated schools were run on secular basis (Sheffield, 2009). At independence in 1963; the Kenyan government recognized the role played by church missionaries in the promotion of education. The schools that were established by the church remained under the sponsorship of those churches but registered as public schools.

After independence the new Kenyan government through an Act of Parliament passed the Education Act in 1968. The Education Act required that the Church hand over the management of schools to the local authority, Chapter 211:8 (3) and assume the role of a sponsor. In 1969 as the Education Act was being implemented, Pope John Paul VI created the Catholic Diocese of Kisii. From then on the Catholic Diocese of Kisii took part in implementation of the Education Act and continued to play a role in provision of Education. This research intends to carry out a case study of Kisii Catholic Diocese role in the provision of education in general and in particular secondary education with a view of finding out what contributions the Catholic Church has made and how its work can be strengthened, so that the church can achieve its basic mission of evangelizing through education.

After independence in 1963, a well defined role emerged for the church in a Nationally centralized system of education for all Kenyans. This role is derived from the following:

1. The ruling political party's manifesto, that is, Kenya African National Union (KANU) manifesto which states, "In the great task of educating our people, the continued participation of the missionaries and other voluntary agencies who have served us so much in the past will be welcomed". (KA.NU Manifesto, 1963).
2. The November 1963 statement by the Christian church which declared that the churches will continue the role of educating the society and endorse the idea that the state should indeed take more and more responsibility for the administration of schools.
3. The Ministry of Education order of 1965, following the Ominde report of 1964 recommended that education was a social service and therefore the responsibility of the government. The Ministry of Education issued an order in 1965 requiring that the churches hand over the schools "voluntarily" to the government. The Catholic church was unwilling to hand over her schools until it was made very clear how it would continue to play its vital role in the new set up. The church felt and still feels that it has an obligation to its followers who are in schools at all levels of education and that an education which does not include religion is incomplete. To enact the recommendations of Ominde's report two crucial bills were introduced in Parliament which became the Teachers Service Commission Act: 1967 Chapter 212 and the Education bill, which became Education Act 1968 Chapter 211 (Republic of Kenya, 1980).

The implementation of these two Acts gave the church the following as its rights, duties and responsibilities in the new system of education in independent Kenya.

1. While teachers have one employer, the Teacher's Service Commission, the Religions personnel, that is, Fathers, Brothers, Sisters, and lay missionaries are seconded to the Ministry of Education.
2. The sponsor may manage schools which are either assisted or unaided. The sponsor is not a manager of Public schools.
3. The secondary school and teacher's colleges are managed by their Board of Governors; the former church manager is a sponsor.
4. The board of governors and sponsor have a serious obligation to maintain the religious tradition of the sponsored schools.
5. The sponsor and his representative shall have the right to enter the sponsored school for the purpose of religious instructions, supervision thereof and for pastoral work among pupils and teachers
6. The sponsor shall have the right to use of the building during out of school hours free of charge. The sponsor will be responsible for any damage incurred during that period of use.
7. A reasonable and adequate amount of the usual equipment grant to school will "be used to provide religious textbooks and teaching aids recommended by the sponsor. This was applicable during the time when Kenya School Equipment Scheme was in operation.
8. The sponsor has got the right of consultation in the appointment of staff in schools.
9. The sponsor may have, during normal school days, a religious day of observance.
10. The sponsor, in consultation with the Head teacher of the sponsored school can increase the minimum number of three obligatory periods of religious instructions a week in the school to four or five in a week.
11. The sponsor and the Head teacher should make sure adequate attention is given to teaching of religion.
12. The appointment of a school Head of a sponsored school under a Board of Governors shall be made by the Teacher's Service Commission in consultation with and as far as possible with the agreement of the sponsor.
13. There is freedom of religion in Kenyan schools.

It has to be noted that this Education Act and the subsequent regulations issued concerning its implementation are the ones in force up to the present (Republic of Kenya, 1980). According to Kanuku (2009), a church is a local assembly of believers as well as the redeemed of all ages who follow Jesus Christ as Saviour and Lord; it is a community of Christians who believe in and follow Christ without reference to locality or limits. People see the church as a social organization with good moral values and are able to extend a helping hand to the needy.

According to Kenya Episcopal Conference (2000), the Catholic Church is under an obligation to promote the welfare of the whole life of man, she has therefore a part to play in the development and extension of education. (Vatican II document 1962-1965). There

are twelve principles which guide the contribution of the church in education; they are enunciated by the documents of Vatican II, and reiterated by the booklet of the sacred congregation for Catholic education. They underlie the continued involvement of the church everywhere in education as part of her mission to humanity and are applied to each natural situation as the Episcopal conference see fit (Kenya Episcopal Conference, 2000). The principles of Catholic Christian Education include:

1. The church has a right and duty to establish schools: "The churches involvement in the field of education is demonstrated especially by the Catholic School". The Church continues to establish schools, these schools are not sectarian nor are they for proselytizing. In Kenya this is done in accordance with the guarantee of Religious freedom in the constitution of Kenya and in accordance with the Education Act 2013. Sections 7 and 26.
2. The Catholic School should promote Catholic values: Schools which are in any way depended on the Church should conform as far as possible to the ideal of a Catholic School, though Catholic Schools can take on forms which vary according to local circumstances. Those running such schools are invited to constantly evaluated their work and ask what Catholic Values they are promoting in their school or institutions. (Kenya Episcopal Conference, 2000).
3. The Catholic Church has an obligation III the sphere of higher Education. "The church anticipates great benefits from the activities of the faculties of sacred sciences". (Kenya Episcopal Conference, 2000).
4. All Catholic Education efforts need, Co-ordination. "As Co-operation, which is becoming daily more important and more effective at Diocesan, national and international levels it is very necessary in educational sphere."(Kenya Episcopal Conference, 2000).

According to Christian Missionaries to Kenya, an education that was not provided by the church was incomplete; the school was the focal point of attracting the heathens and a means through which a native leadership in the church could be trained (Regnerus, 2007). The Phelps-stokes Commission of 1924 had earlier strengthened this co-operation between the colonial government and the missionaries where the government was to let the religious initiated schools in the hands of that church. Provision of education is seen as a vehicle for progressive development. That is why it was given prominence in the Kenya Education Act 2013. The Act allowed an agreement to be made between the Ministry of Education and the sponsoring Churches as regards the rights and responsibilities of the Church sponsor in management of schools in Kenya (Banr, 2010). According to the Ministry of Education (Republic of Kenya, 1980), the Board of Governors Order amplifies section 11 which allows the sponsor to propose the chairman of the school Board who should be ratified by the Minister of Education. A vote was required ratify the selection of the chairman by the ten (10) initial members appointed by the minister of education following a nomination exercise in which a panel was chaired by the Sub - County education officer or his representative. The earlier Education Act also allowed the sponsor to prepare and recommend for approval by the Ministry the learning resources for religious education in sponsored schools (Regulation, 5), (Republic of Kenya, 1980). It is therefore evident from the foregone high lights of rights and responsibilities that the sponsor is a key figure in the management of church sponsored schools.

Mabeya, Ndiku and Njino (2010) in their study on role of Church sponsor in the management of secondary schools: impact on academic performance and conflict concern in Kenya, viewed the school as a social system with a series of sub-systems within it which interact with each other and the environment. Such school sub-systems include sponsors, teachers, head teachers, BOM, PA, students and support staff. They argued that for the school to achieve its goals and objectives effectively, the subsystems should interact harmoniously. They concentrated on the role of Church sponsor in secondary schools, zeroed in on Impact on academic performance and conflict concerns between the sponsors and the school management in Kenya. The results obtained from the analysis showed that there was a significant relationship between the role of the sponsor in the provision of a conducive learning environment and academic performance. On the roles of the sponsor in school management, the findings revealed that all the church sponsors 97(100%) contributed to the maintenance of religious traditions and church doctrines in schools. This supports the historical traditions of the church missionaries' intention in the introduction of formal education where the school was looked at as a media of evangelization (Sheffied, 1994). This was followed by giving consent of appointment of head teachers 87(90%) and ensuring that the schools' infrastructure and assets are well kept. The issue of supervising and ensuring that religious education was taught in school was rated 40 (41%) which supports the Kenya Catholic Episcopal that a sponsored school curriculum should include a substantial religious education programme that is life centered, broad, multifaceted as well as personal growth. The curriculum should be rooted in the church traditions and ways that nurture spiritual development (Kenya Catholic Episcopal, 2000).

According to Makokha (2002), the curriculum and extra-curriculum activities in sponsored schools reflect the spirit of the sponsor. Therefore, Christian religious education is to be taught in all sponsored schools up to form four. The pastoral programme is expected to be taught as regards to the preservation of the church doctrine. Learners should be given freedom of participating in church oriented associations like young Christian associations, legion of Mary and others. They therefore did not deal with the contribution of the Catholic Church, hence left a gap on the actual contributions of the Catholic Church in terms of financial and instructional resources.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON CONTRIBUTION OF THE CATHOLIC CHURCH TO FINANCIAL AND INFRASTRUCTURAL RESOURCES OF SCHOOLS

According to Opey and Carr (1982), in England, State-run schools and colleges are financed through national taxation, and take pupils free of charge between the ages of 3 and 18. The schools may levy charges for activities such as swimming, theatre visits and field trips, provided the charges are voluntary, thus ensuring that those who cannot afford to pay are allowed to participate in such events. Approximately 93% of English school children attend such schools. A significant minority of state-funded schools are faith schools, which are attached to religious groups, most often the Church of England or the Roman Catholic Church. There is also a small number of state funded boarding schools, which typically charge for board but not tuition. Boarding fees are limited to £12,000 per annum. Nearly 90% of state-funded secondary schools are specialist schools, receiving extra funding to develop one or more subjects in which the school specializes. Muller and Ellison (2009) adds that in Britain for example, the churches sponsor individual students for various courses in different institutions, regardless of them being private or government owned. There is a clear cut policy in terms of management between the private, church – owned and government schools. This is the opposite both in Kenya and Kisii Central where the two interest groups claim a stake in running of public secondary schools.

The reviewed studies by Muller and Ellison (2009), focused on the contribution of the Catholic Church in Britain in terms of the Catholic Church's sponsorship of individual students for various courses in different institutions, regardless of them being private or government owned; but did not deal with the contribution of the Catholic Church to financing of education in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub-County.

Catholic education in New Zealand, as Neal (2008) puts it, was first introduced following the arrival of the first Catholic Bishop, Jean Baptiste Pompallier in 1838. A year after signing the Treaty of Waitangi, the first Catholic school in New Zealand was developed in Auckland on 1841. The schools were originally managed by seven sisters from Ireland and aimed to assist the Maori population and the new settlers. From 1853 to 1875, the provincial governments financed grants for the Catholic schools. The Education Act 1877, however, allowed all schools to be free, compulsory and secular, and therefore disallowing funding of Catholic schools. It was only after the passing of the Private Schools Conditional Integration Act 1975 in which Catholic schools were integrated with the State education system with the State being able to assist in operating Catholic schools (Fagan, 2010).

Fagan, (2010) adds that, the Catholic schools are owned by a proprietor, typically by the Bishop of the diocese. Currently, Catholic schools in New Zealand are termed 'state integrated schools' for funding purposes, meaning that teachers' salaries, learning materials, and operations of the school (e.g. power and gas) are publicly funded, but the school property is not. New Zealand Catholic schools are built on land owned by the diocese; if the government was to fund Catholic school property maintenance and capital works above the entitlement of any other private property owner, it would be transferring wealth to the bishop, breaking the separation of church and state. Instead, parents of students at Catholic schools pay "attendance dues" to the proprietors to fund property costs. According to Kanuku (2009), people see the church as a social organization with good moral values and are able to extend a helping hand to the needy. Indeed, the Catholic Code of Canon Law, Can 795, as quoted by Koech (1992), states that, "education must pay regard to the formation of the whole person, so that all may attain their eternal destiny and at the same time promote the common good of society. Children and young persons are therefore to be cared for in such a way that their physical, moral and intellectual talents may develop in a harmonious manner, so that they may attain a greater sense of responsibility and a right of use of freedom, and be formed to take an active part in social life". P. 7

In United States of America, according to Neal (2008), the Catholic Church liaises with private organizations to fund schools. Such organizations include The Raskob Foundation which is a private, independent Catholic foundation that provides monetary support to institutions that identify with the Roman Catholic Church. Its Board of Trustees meets twice a year to sort through grant applications and dole out awards. While applications requesting funds for construction projects are not high on the list of priorities

for the Raskob Foundation, it does occasionally grant financial assistance to those Catholic churches looking to make renovations. It offers a maximum of \$200,000 per project for such grantees. Any churches with building or renovation projects that exceed that amount must prove that they already have 50 percent of the cost in hand and that construction is already underway.

Another of such kind is The Koch Foundation is an independent, private organization whose sole purpose is to provide funding for projects that spread the Catholic faith. Since its inception in the late 1970s, the foundation has awarded more than \$100 million to Catholic organizations across the globe. The amount of the grants given varies from project to project, and organizations should specifically detail their proposed budgets within their applications (Muller & Ellison, 2009).

In Asia, a number of programmes have been put in place; for example, St. Ann Parish (Lafayette) Educational Assistance Fund. The purposes of the Fund shall be to provide scholarships to Catholic students at St. Ann Parish in Lafayette, who meet certain criteria; who are attending or plan to attend any Catholic parochial school operated by another Catholic parish within Tippecanoe County, and as well to defray costs incurred by the St. Ann Parish in sponsoring and operating religious classes or programs (Regnerus, 2011).

In South Africa, during the twentieth century, mission education began to reflect several postmodern characteristics identified by Neal. The most prominent was its opposition to the prevalent racial thinking and practice in South Africa during this period which reflected Enlightenment reasoning along linear-causal lines. Black education in South Africa during the early twentieth century was still largely a mission endeavour, which functioned within a highly racist society which adhered to ideas of European racial supremacy. Government policies of segregation, as well as prevalent theories and practices on race, provide but a few examples which formed the backdrop for mission education. That these styles of thinking and policies and their subsequent actions would influence the education that missionaries provided for Black people in both the nineteenth and twentieth century, is given, due to the fact that education does not function within a vacuum, and would obviously affect the way that missionaries imparted their knowledge, either bolstering or defying prevalent forms of knowledge and cognitive styles (Neal, 2008). For example, a post-World War One movement evident in South Africa which articulated the tenets of scientific racism was the eugenics movement. Mission education also reflected the colonial government's policies of expansion. Whereas previously mission education had reflected a classical curriculum, during the mid-nineteenth century it began to emphasize industrial education and training (Neal, 2008). The Church sponsors children who were disadvantaged through payment of fees, buying uniforms and provision of meals in Kenya. They fully or partly (with the help of fee paying parents) sponsored pre-schools in which Christian values were taught as part of the curriculum. Their policy was to bring up children in a Godly manner by developing them spiritually, physically, socially and in wisdom, (Kenya Episcopal Conference, 2000).

In the USA, construction grants can go towards the building of new schools or the renovations of old ones. Catholic churches often need a great deal of financial support from patrons or Catholic organizations before they can begin construction or renovation projects. Several private, independent Catholic organizations exist solely to provide resources and funding to such churches, particularly those in underdeveloped or impoverished areas. School construction grants provide large amounts of funding to educational facilities, ranging from pre - kindergarten to college. Schools that are eligible for these are grants must prove need for work that promotes heightened environmentally friendly schools, Sub - Countys and neighborhood. Along with improving the sustainability of a building, construction on a school must also relate specifically to improving the quality of education. These eligible repairs relate to expanding classrooms or the school structure itself, repairing worn-down facilities and updating old equipment (Cheruiyot, 2009).

The Academic Research Infrastructure program (ARI) grant aims to update academic research facilities, in educational facilities such as schools and also in museums and laboratories. The goal is to improve research facilities to aid in more hands-on learning environments. The grant is not specifically for the creation of new research structures, but rather for repairing or updating existing research facilities. Grant awards can reach over \$2,000,000. Requests for grants under \$2,000,000 do not require a site visit by the NSF. To apply, all interested candidates must submit a grant proposal to the National Science Foundation (Muller & Ellison, 2009). According to Muller and Ellison, (2009), under the American Recovery and Investment Act of 2009, grants titled ;discretionary grants; can be awarded to K-12 schools for a wide array of construction projects aimed at helping improve the existing structure of the school. Grants can help cover the costs of preparing construction plans and obtaining necessary resources, as well as repairing and expanding school classrooms. Grants can also cover the costs of updating facilities like libraries and laboratories. Award values vary in relation to the amount requested for each project. The reviewed studies by Muller and Ellison (2009), focused on the

contribution of the Catholic Church in the US in terms of Grants can help cover the costs of preparing construction plans and obtaining necessary resources, as well as repairing and expanding school classrooms; but did not deal with the contribution of the Catholic Church to infrastructural resources in Kisii Central Sub-County.

In Uganda, the Catholic Church in Uganda has shouldered the leadership in the area of education by establishing educational facilities at all levels including the numerous primary schools, secondary schools and tertiary institutions of education which are exemplified by the existence of Catholic founded colleges, seminaries and the Uganda Martyrs University at Nkozi in Uganda. According to Olive, (1952), speaking about development relative to the contribution of the Catholic Church one would be facing a gap if one would not give some attention to the Encyclical Letter of Pope Paul VI titled *Populorum Progression* that is “The Development of Peoples.”

In Liberia, diplomatic relationships between the Vatican and Liberia were established in 1927, celebrated by a spectacular and massive march through the streets of Monrovia on the feast of Christ the King, which subsequently boosted registration in Catholic schools and a lasting foundation of Catholicism, hence assisted in building schools especially secondary schools in rural and remote areas (Mbatia & Mureu, 2008).

Mwangangi (2000) in his study, *The Role of The Catholic Church In Provision of Education In General and in Particular Primary Education: A Case Study of Machakos Catholic Diocese, Kenya*, intended to carry out a case study of Machakos Catholic Diocese role in the provision of education in general and in particular primary education with a view of finding out what role the Catholic church has done and how its work can be strengthened, so that the church can achieve its basic mission of evangelizing through education. The study found that the Catholic Diocese of Machakos has helped in setting up and sponsor 352 primary schools within the Diocese out of a total of 1346 primary schools. This represents 26% of the total number of primary schools within the Diocese, which covers Machakos and Makueni Districts. Twenty-six (26) per cent is far below the expectations of the Catholic faithfuls and priests who feel very strongly that the diocese should be hundred (100) per cent involved in provision of Education. The Catholic Diocese of Machakos has helped set up and sponsor 91 secondary schools out of a total of 252 secondary schools within the Catholic Diocese of Machakos. This represents thirty-six (36) per cent of the secondary schools and is far below expectations of Catholics in the Diocese who are for hundred (100) per cent involvement of the church in provision of education.

In Kenya, the earlier missionaries did a lot of work in as far as development of school physical facilities is concerned. With the coming of the Church Missionary Society during the colonial days assisted in opening new schools in the whole country. In Kisii, the Catholic Church built schools; among them, Cardinal Otunga Mosocho, Nyabururu Girls and Sameta Boys, and others that followed later. From this time, according to Cheruiyot (2008), it is not easy to draw a line to separate the sponsor and the sponsored. The question commonly asked is, who actually sponsors the other between the school and the church? He adds, ‘the modern day sponsorship is a matter of a school identifying itself with a school that is starting and in most cases, the community is forced to contribute towards the provision of physical facilities. It is however worth noting that many of the sponsored schools are built on the Church lands, in which case the title deeds are kept by the Church (Makabila, 2010).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework is a research tool intended to assist a researcher to develop awareness and understanding of the situation under scrutiny. It has a potential usefulness as a tool to assist a researcher to make meaning of subsequent findings. It forms part of the agenda for negotiation to be scrutinized and tested, reviewed and reformed as a result of investigation (Okumbe, 2009). The study was guided by the conceptual framework and whose operation is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework showing Contribution of the Catholic Church to School Financial and Infrastructural resources.

The conceptual framework (Figure 1) shows that the Catholic Church plays an integral part in the provision of financial resources and infrastructural development. Value addition takes various forms, for example, provision of money, materials and advice. This value addition is measured in terms of rating scale on the Provision of Financial Resource and Provision of Infrastructural Resources. It therefore means that, if the Catholic Church is effectively involved in the management of Public Secondary school, the school can perform well in quality index and maintain the good performance over the years, the school should enjoy prudent financial management, the school should have improved and well managed physical infrastructure and lastly the appointment of school administrators namely the Board of Governors, the Principal and the Deputy Principal should be on merit. On the contrary, if the sponsor is ineffective in management of public secondary school, the school will suffer negatively in that – there will be poor academic performance, there will be poor financial management the physical infrastructure of the school will be wasted or managed and lastly, the school administrators may end up being incompetent and inefficient.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive survey design. The study targeted 132 respondents in 32 public Catholic Church sponsored secondary schools within Kisii Central Sub-County. The population comprised of 29 principals, 29 deputy principals, 29 Board of Management chair persons, 29 PA chair persons, 1 Education Secretary, 1 Staffing officer, 1 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standard Officer and 1 Sub County Director of Education. Saturated sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The study used questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis guides to collect data. Face validity of the instruments was determined by the help of experts in the field. Reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained for the questionnaire hence the instrument was reliable for the study. The quantitative data was analyzed using frequency counts, means and regression analysis. Qualitative data obtained through the use of interview schedules was transcribed and analyzed thematically as themes and sub-themes emerged.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Gender of the Respondents

The gender of the respondents was as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	27	94.7
Female	2	5.3
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

The finding in Table 1 reveals that the majority 27 (94.7%) of the respondents were males, and 2 (5.3%) were females. This result implies that the male gender dominates the female counterparts in securing the responsibilities in managing the secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. It was clear that this lacked the one third gender rule as stipulated in the Kenyan Constitution.

Table 2: Qualification of the Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
Diploma	2	5.3
B. Ed	13	47.4
M.Ed	5	15.8
MBA	2	5.3
PHD	2	5.3
PGDE	5	15.8
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 2 shows that 2(5.3%) of the respondents had Diploma in education, 13(47.4%) of them had B.Ed, 5(15.8%) of the respondents had M.Ed, 2(5.3%) of them had MBA, 2(5.3%) of them had PhD, 5(15.8%) of them had PGDE. The study finding indicates that 52(47.3%) of the respondent had post graduate studies, and another 52(47.4%) had bachelors in education. Only 6(5.3%) of the respondents had diploma in education. It was evident that the study population was able to tackle the research questionnaire with minimal assistance from the researcher and also they were conversant and had know-how on educational matters.

Table 3: Leadership Experience

Year	Frequency	Percent
3 – 5	6	21.3
6-10	9	26.9
11-14	7	24.1
15 – 20	5	20.3
21 and above	2	7.4
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

The study finding in Table 3 reveals that 6(21.3%) of the respondents had 3-5 years of leadership experience in a Catholic sponsored secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County, 9(26.9%) of them had 6-10 years of leadership experience, 7(24.1%) of the respondents had 11-14 years of leadership experience and 5(20.3%) of them had 15-20 years of leadership experience. Only 2(7.4%) of the respondents had 21years and above in leadership experience in a Catholic sponsored secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. The research result indicates that 23(79.1%) of the respondents had more than 5 years leadership experience. Therefore,

this implied that the respondents were able to answer appropriately on the issues addressed by the study and had first-hand information in the education sector in Kisii Central Sub - County.

Table 4: Type of School

Type of school	Frequency	Percent
Public Day	26	89.5
Boarding	3	10.5
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

According to Table 4, the findings shows that 26(89.5%) of the secondary schools in Kisii Sub - County were public day, and 3(10.5%) were boarding secondary school. The finding indicates clearly that majority were public day schools. It therefore showed that the Catholic Church concentrated more on the public day secondary schools which were situated in rural areas hence more needy.

Table 5: Year of Establishment

Year	Frequency	Percent
1961-1973	5	16.4
1974-1986	0	0.0
1987-1999	9	31.8
2000-2012	15	51.8
Total	29	100.0

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 5 indicates that 5(16.4%) of the schools were established between 1961 and 1973, 9(31.8%) of the secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County were established between 1974 and 1999, while 15(51.8%) of them were established in 2000 – 2012. The study finding implies that more than half of the secondary schools were established below the year 2000. It is evident that Catholic Church has sponsored many secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County in the early 60s and late 90s. More schools have been sponsored between 2000 and 2012 which was an indication that the church had increased its sponsorship of the schools over the years.

Objective One

The research objective was to establish contribution of Catholic Church to financing of education in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County.

The Principals were asked to rate on a 5-point rating scale the contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources used in public secondary schools that they sponsor. The results were as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Catholic Church Contribution to Financial resources

Ratings	Contribution Index	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Mean
1.00 – 1.44	1	0	0	
1.45-2.44	2	15	51.8	
2.45-3.44	3	8	26.4	
3.45-4.44	4	3	10.9	
4.50-5.00	5	3	10.9	
Total		29	100.0	2.79

Interpretation of contribution Index:

1 -Very Low 2 - Low 3 - Moderate 4 - High 5 - Very High

Source: Field Data (2015)

Table 6 shows that the overall mean on the Catholic Church’s contribution of financial resources to schools was 2.79 that was moderate contribution. To establish the contribution of the Catholic Church to financial resources in enhancement of public secondary school management quality indices of schools was established for purposes of correlation (as shown in Table 7).

Contribution of the Catholic Church to financial resources in enhancement of secondary school management analysis is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Contribution of the Catholic Church to financial resources and school management Quality Index

		Management of Public Secondary Schools
Financial Resources	Pearson Correlation	.550
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	29

Source: Field Data (2015)

From Table 7 it can be noted that the relationship between contribution of the Catholic Church to financial resources and Quality index was strong positive and moderate ($r = .550, N=29, P < .05$). There exists strong, positive contribution, hence the relationship was high. This means that the financial contribution by the Catholic Church resulted to moderate improvement in the school management Quality Index. To estimate the contribution of the Catholic Church, regression analysis was computed and the results were as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression analysis of financial resources and Quality Index

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.550 ^a	.303	.277	.532	.303	11.734	1	27	.002	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Financial resources

b. Dependent Variable: QUALITY-INDEX

From Table 8, it can be noted that the Catholic Church accounted for 27.7% of variation in Quality Index as signified by the coefficient .277. The other 72.3% was due to other factors that were not subject of the study, for example, teachers, government, student characteristics and attitudes. To confirm whether the Catholic Church’s contribution was a significant predictor, ANOVA was computed (Table 9).

Table 9: Computation of ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.322	1	3.322	.002 ^b
	Residual	7.644	27	.283	
	Total	10.966	28		

a. Dependent Variable: QUALITY-INDEX

b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial-Resources

From Table 9 it can be observed that the Catholic Church contribution was a significant predictor of school management Quality Index ((1, 27) = 3.322, $P < .05$). To compute the actual contribution, simple regression analysis was computed (Table 10).

Table 10 Simple regression analysis of Catholic Church financial contribution and school management Quality Index

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	.946	.313		3.019	.005	.303	
Financial Resources	.384	.112	.550	3.425	.002	.154	.614

a. Dependent Variable: QUALITY-INDEX

From Table 10, it can be noted that one unit increase in Catholic Church contribution to financial resources will improve school management by .384 units. Regression Equation therefore is $Y = .946 + .384X$.

Objective Two

The research objective was to establish contribution of Catholic Church to infrastructural resources of secondary school administrators in public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub – County.

The Principals were asked to rate on a 5-point rating scale the contribution of the Catholic Church to infrastructural resources used in public secondary schools that they sponsor. The results were as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: The Catholic Church Contribution to Infrastructural Resources in Public Secondary Schools

Mean Ratings	Contribution Index	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Mean
1.00 – 1.44	1	0	0.0	
1.45 – 2.44	2	4	15.5	
2.45 – 3.44	3	6	20.9	
3.45 – 4.44	4	17	58.2	
4.50 – 5.00	5	2	5.4	
Total		29	100.0	3.71

Interpretation of Contribution Index: 1 -Very Low 2 - Low 3 - Moderate
 4 - High 5 - Very High

Table 11 shows that the overall mean on the Catholic Church’s contribution of infrastructural resources to schools was 3.71 that was a moderate contribution. To establish the contribution of the Catholic Church to instructional resources in enhancement of public secondary school management quality indices of schools was established for purposes of correlation (as shown in Table 12). Contribution of the Catholic Church to infrastructural resources in enhancement of secondary school management analysis is shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Contribution of the Catholic Church to Infrastructural Resources and School management Quality Index

		Management of Public Sec. Schools
Infrastructural-Resources	Pearson Correlation	.622
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	29

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From Table 13 it can be noted that the relationship between contribution of the Catholic Church to infrastructural resources and Quality index was positive and moderate ($r = .622, N=29, P < .05$). To estimate the contribution of the Catholic Church, regression analysis was computed and the results were as shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Regression analysis of Infrastructural resources and management Quality Index

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Sig. Change	F	
				R Square Change	F Change	df1			df2
1	.622 ^a	.387	.364	.499	.387	17.040	1	27	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Infrastructural-Resources

b. Dependent Variable: QUALITY-INDEX

From Table 14, it can be noted that the Catholic Church accounted for 36.4% of variation in Quality Index as signified by the coefficient .364. The other 63.6% was due to other factors that were not subject of the study, for example, teachers, government, student characteristics and attitudes.

To confirm whether the Catholic Church’s infrastructural contribution was a significant predictor to the school Quality Index, ANOVA was computed (Table 15).

Table 15: Computation of ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	4.243	1	4.243	17.040	.000 ^b
Residual	6.723	27	.249		
Total	10.966	28			

a. Dependent Variable: Quality-Index

b. Predictors: (Constant), Infrastructural-Resources

From Table 15 it can be observed that the Catholic Church contribution was a significant predictor of school management Quality Index ($(1, 27) = 17.040, P < .05$). To compute the actual contribution, simple regression analysis was computed (Table 16).

Table 16: Simple Regression Analysis of Catholic Church Infrastructural Contribution and school management Quality Index

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.989	.254		3.895	.001	.468	
	Infrastructural Resources	.363	.088	.622	4.128	.000	.183	.543

a. Dependent Variable: Quality-Index

From Table 16, it can be noted that one unit increase in Catholic Church contribution to infrastructural resources will improve school management by .363 units. Regression Equation therefore is $Y = .989 + .363X$.

DISCUSSION

During the interview schedules, the finding of the study revealed secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County received financial support from the Catholic Church. Education secretary said: In most cases, the public secondary schools received about Kshs. 1,000,000.00 in the 2014 as follows: school serial numbers 5, 12, 15, 16, 19, 22, 23 and 27 each received Kshs. 95, 000 from the catholic church and its partners to support the students' and teachers', lunch programmes totaling to Kshs. 760, 000. We also disbursed Kshs. 50, 000 each to school serial numbers 2, 13, 16 and 31, totaling to Kshs. 200, 000, while school 25 received Kshs. 40, 000 for the purchase of school uniforms to needy students. " Similar comments were reported from the Sub County Quality Assurance and Standard Officer: "some schools in Kisii Central Sub - County got some funds from various sponsors and development partners."

The Sub County Director of Education added: "However, some schools administrators did corrupt the use of these funds for their personal use instead of the intended one. This affects the quality of school performance." Document analysis in the trial balances revealed that the schools had received about Ksh. 1,000,000.00 in 2014 to support lunch programmes and school uniforms for students in line with the academic programmes in the schools. The monetary allocation to public secondary schools is very significant in ensuring that the required learning facilities are availed to the students for good academic performance. Despite the fact that government through the Ministry of Education Science and Technology (MOEST) was providing Free Secondary Education funds to public secondary schools to the tune of Kshs. 12, 870 per student per year (Republic of Kenya, 2015), in most cases, they are inadequate because students' requirements based on the curriculum demands are more than what is provided. As a result principals of schools request stakeholders to supplement the government effort in provision of school requirements. This is in consistent with requirements of the basic education Act 2013 which requires that the sponsor should be actively involved in the school development in terms of students' spiritual growth and implementation of the curriculum (Republic of Kenya, 2013). This contribution varies from school to school depending on the level of need and interest of the school management. However, the school administrators should be encouraged to use the funds they receive from donors in the right and intended use.

The study finding agrees with Muller and Ellison (2009) who established that Catholic Schools in the United States benefit from the financial support from the Koch Foundation. The finding concurs with Neal (2008) who said that Catholic Church liaises with private organizations to fund schools to the tune of \$200, 000 per project in grants. In addition, the findings indicated that the Catholic Church provided financial support to students in terms of scholarships and bursaries to needy students from the sponsored schools. The education secretary was reported to have said: Majority of the students in our public secondary schools have benefited from sponsorship awards for their studies and also some have benefited from bursaries provided by the Church. Over Kshs.1, 000, 000.00 have been disbursed to cater for the orphans and less fortunate but bright students in the society. The students received Kshs. 8, 000 each to support their studies.

Also the Staffing officer mentioned; "some students have obtained bursaries from their sponsors and also from the Constituency Development Fund Bursary to help them in studies. Moreover, the Government has provided some subsidiary school fees support to every student through the Ministry of Education." The finding is evident that students benefited from financial support by the sponsors. The financial support is significant to the student's academic life. It helps the student in concentrating in their academics and thus will enhance their academic performance. While document analysis from the fees registers of various schools revealed that, majority of the students in public secondary schools have benefited from sponsorship awards for their studies and also some have benefited from bursaries provided by the Church. Over Ksh. 1,000,000.00 had been disbursed to cater for the orphans and less fortunate but bright students in the society. Moreover, the Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer said; "during Prize giving days, sponsors are normally awarding the best performing teachers and students in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education Examination (KCSE)."

It was evident that public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County received financial motivation. The sponsors considered honoring the hardworking staffs and students by providing some cash to them. This indeed was deemed necessary in boosting the morale of the administration, teachers and students. Document analysis on the various school education days' budgets and programmes revealed that during Prize giving days, sponsor normally awarded the best performing teachers and students in KCSE, to the tune of Kshs. 1,000 per mean grade A for motivation of students and teachers. This was a powerful motivating tool to drive the students and the teachers to work even harder and achieve good results.

Education has in the recent past become very competitive with fewer opportunities available for increasing student population for Universities and other middle - level colleges. It is in this regard that it has become a common norm for school managements to strive and ensure that their students achieve the best result in order to compete favourably with the rest for the chances. Such measures include financial motivation to both teachers and the students, and the school administration also inclusive. Such are usually not budgeted for in the schools' normal budgeting programmes. Therefore, the management of the schools must look for such funds from other donors. The Catholic Church has come out to be one of those donors that keep such school programme going, hence assisting in making the sponsored schools achieve their curriculum objectives. In most cases, good performers are given financial rewards to motivate them and even other students in lower classes and teachers to perform in future.

The study is in agreement with Muller and Ellison (2009) which highlights that churches sponsor individual students for various courses in different institutions, regardless of them being private or government owned. Similarly, the study concurs with Fagan (2010) who stated that Catholic schools are also benefiting from the state funding to cater for teachers salaries, learning materials and operations of the schools. However, neither Muller and Ellison nor Fagan gave the specific situations in which the Catholic Church gave financial motivation to students or teachers as was seen in Kisii Central Sub-County. In addition to the above, qualitative data from questionnaires revealed that 92(88.7%) of Despite the fact that the Ministry of education through Free Secondary Education provides money at Kshs. 12, 870 per student per year, (Republic of Kenya, 2015) in most cases, they are inadequate because students' curriculum requirements are more than what is provided by the government. As a result principals of schools request stakeholders to supplement the government effort in provision further funding. This is in consistent with requirements of the basic education Act 2013 which requires that the sponsor should be actively involved in the school development in terms of students' spiritual growth and implementation of the curriculum. This contribution varies from school to school depending on the level of need and interest of the school management. It also depends on the degree of needs of the students in question and their family backgrounds. The sponsor can provide the equipment through the BOM or on request by the school administration.

According to Opey and Carr (1982), in England, State-run schools and colleges are financed through national taxation, and take pupils free of charge between the ages of 3 and 18. A significant minority of state-funded schools are faith schools, which are attached to religious groups, most often the Church of England the Roman Catholic Church. There are also a small number of state funded boarding schools, which typically charge for board but not tuition. Boarding fees are limited to £12,000 per annum. Nearly 90% of state-funded secondary schools are specialist schools, receiving extra funding to develop one or more subjects in which the school specializes from church sponsors. Muller and Ellison (2009) adds that in Britain for example, the churches sponsor individual students for various courses in different institutions, regardless of them being private or government owned. There is a clear cut policy in terms of management between the private, church – owned and government schools. Further, the study findings reveal that the sponsor's financial motivation to teachers, students or entire administration was in place. According to Education secretary there was financial motivation to teachers whose subjects are performing well in the KCSE. The education secretary was noted saying: In most of our schools teachers whose subjects show good performance are awarded with some shopping vouchers. Also the best performing students are awarded Kshs. 1,000 for every student attained Grade A. In addition, teachers are given some money when they offer extra teaching schedules. The respondents stated that sponsor is a capable of more financial contribution in schools. On the other hand 18 (16.4%) of the respondents indicated that sponsor was not capable of more financial contribution in schools. This shows that the sponsor had the ability in terms of resources to change its policy of financial support to schools and assist more in running the curriculum programmes. Therefore the study may be a useful tool to the sponsors to increase funding to the school's academic programmes.

The finding of the study indicates that the sponsor's involvement in the infrastructural management of secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub – County was significant. Findings from the interview schedules show that indeed the Catholic Church has played key role in infrastructural management of secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. Education Secretary said; "in some cases, public schools received money for building libraries, laboratories and classrooms. In Kisii Central Sub - County over 10 libraries have been constructed, 5 Laboratories new built and more than 20 classrooms were constructed by the Catholic Church." The Sub County Director of Education mentioned that; "sponsors have really tried in constructing classes and laboratories in the public sponsored secondary schools within Kisii Central Sub - County. Over Ksh.100,000,000 have been spent in improving the infrastructure in the public secondary schools in the Sub - County." Document analysis guides indicated that most public schools

received money for building libraries, laboratories and classrooms. Over 10 libraries had been constructed, 5 science laboratories built and more than 26 classrooms were constructed by the Catholic Church over a period of 15 years in Kisii Central Sub - County. Over Kshs. 100,000,000.00 had been spent in improving the infrastructure of the sponsored public schools in the Sub - County.

The government sends money to schools to assist them put up more physical facilities, as well as improving the existing ones through the school infrastructure improvement fund. In addition, the parents have been called upon to pay development levies, which are also meant for the same purpose. This money from MOEST and parents is however not usually enough; a situation that always forces the principals to look for extra support from other key stakeholders of education, including the Catholic Church in order to effectively achieve this objective. School physical facilities add the aesthetic value of a school, brings comfort and friendly learning environment, all of which contribute to a child friendly school (Rosenholtz & Rosenholtz, 2010). A good learning school environment by extension leads to motivated learners who eventually results in good performance in KCSE. This was very important to schools since it helped the schools to achieve more effective in service delivery and also improves the management Quality Indices of these schools. Therefore, there is need for the sponsors to facilitate infrastructural development in the public secondary schools.

The finding concurs with Cheruiyot (2009) who affirmed that Catholic Church in the USA provide a great deal of financial support to build new schools and renovation of the old ones. This differs slightly as in Kisii Central; the Church sometimes did the actual construction. Further, the study finding reveals that land was a major aspect of the school infrastructure that the Catholic Church had invested in heavily. The findings from the interview schedules reveal that public secondary schools were offered land for building infrastructure that helps in learning process. During the interview, the education secretary was reported to have said; “over 20 public secondary schools within Kisii Central Sub - County are given land by the church. Church offered the land and keeps the title deed in the Dioceses offices.” Sub County Quality Assurance and Standard Office 4 said; “in most of schools within Kisii Central Sub - County they have large track of land offered by the Sponsors such as the church and also some by the community giving the community lands to schools free of charge for building laboratories, classrooms and play fields.” At the same time the Sub County Director of Education (SCDE) said; “it is a remarkable effort by the sponsors and the community offering land to our schools in Kisii Central Sub - County. This is commendable in improving the standards of education in our public secondary schools.” Document analysis on the title deeds revealed that nearly all the schools had been constructed on land contributed by the sponsor, with the title deeds written in the Church’s name, and kept by the Church for purposes of avoiding misuse by the school administrators.

The finding clearly indicates that public secondary schools in Kisii Central Sub - County had benefited from land contribution by the sponsors. This is very important in the provision of space to build infrastructure in the schools. Land is a vital asset for every school in terms of playing grounds, class rooms, laboratories and pilot farms for the agriculture students. This is in consistent with requirements of the basic education Act 2013 which requires that the sponsor should be actively involved in the school development in terms of students’ spiritual growth and implementation of the curriculum. This contribution varies from school to school depending on the level of need and interest of the school management. Most of the schools started by the Catholic Church, however received bigger land sizes, as big as 20 hectares, compared to those started after the 1990s. This is due to the pressure of land in Gusii land, with no room for expansion, coupled with exorbitant land prices. The sponsor can provide the land through the community, BOM or on request by the school administration.

Fagan, (2010) concurs with the findings that, the Catholic schools are owned by a proprietor, typically by the Bishop of the diocese. New Zealand Catholic schools are built on land owned by the diocese; if the government was to fund Catholic school property maintenance and capital works above the entitlement of any other private property owner, it would be transferring wealth to the bishop, breaking the separation of church and state. On the other hand, the Catholic Church in Kisii Central, in addition to purchasing and owning the school lands, it retained the title deeds to affirm its ownership.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between the Catholic Church’s contribution to financial resources and Quality Index was positive and moderate; hence a significant predictor of school management Quality Index. Provision of financial support to schools would enhance their capacity to acquire missing learning resources. Equally, financial support to needy student would assist to keep them in school. This will assist in reducing illiteracy, with the dangers associated with it, for the society.

The relationship between the Catholic Church's contribution to infrastructural resources and Quality Index was positive and moderate; hence a significant predictor of school management Quality Index. Provision of more physical infrastructure would assist in availing more science laboratories, libraries and classrooms that eventually would reduce congestion hence increase student – teacher interactions. This would go a long way in assisting slow learners and improve their ability to internalize learnt concepts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The church should focus more on tuition facilities like class rooms and computer laboratories as they as they benefit the students directly.
- ii. The Catholic church should concentrate more in contribution of infrastructural support to young and up-coming schools especially those in the rural areas as they were more in need as compared to the established schools.

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